

General superspace Abelian gauge transformations isomorphic to groups of spacetime tetrad Lorentz transformations in four-dimensional Lorentzian flat spacetimes

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We have already proved in previous works that all the local internal gauge groups of transformations associated to the Standard Model are isomorphic to local groups of spacetime tetrad transformations. The point of this note is to find additional isomorphisms between superspace generalized gauge Abelian transformations and spacetime tetrad transformations, following a similar line of reasoning. Riemannian constructions have become important since the new tetrads were introduced. These tetrads have a remarkable number of properties that make them outstanding geometrical tools. They allow for local and covariant diagonalization of stress-energy tensors and the ensuing simplification of differential equations and evolution algorithms. Essentially because of their construction structure. Two elements are fundamental in these new tetrad structures, the skeletons and the gauge vectors. It is precisely these skeletons and gauge vectors that have been used in order to prove the theorems about isomorphisms between local gauge groups like $U(1)$ and $SU(2) \times U(1)$, and the local spacetime groups of tetrad transformations in four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes. We will follow a similar course in this paper in order to prove analogous theorems between local groups of superspace Abelian gauge transformations and local groups of tetrad transformations in four-dimensional Lorentzian flat spacetimes.

I. INTRODUCTION

The fact that several local groups of gauge transformations have been proved isomorphic to local groups of tetrad transformations in four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes encourages us to think about the possibility of similar results for superspace local gauge groups of transformations. The new tetrads introduced in manuscripts^{1,2,3} function as a bridge between both group structures. Because at every point in spacetime they define two orthogonal planes or blades. Plane one spanned by the timelike and one spacelike vector, and the other, plane two, by the remaining two spacelike vectors. These tetrad vectors have two structural components in their construction. One is the skeleton, which is a local gauge invariant. The other is the gauge vector. Gauge vectors are gauge on their own right, and they include gauge in their construction. Under local gauge transformations, the two vectors that span plane one, remain on plane one, and analogous for plane two. This means that the metric tensor remains locally invariant in a manifest way under local gauge transformations. This property is a fundamental stone on which the theorems that prove the isomorphisms between the local gauge groups of the Standard Model and local groups of tetrad transformations are demonstrated. In the Abelian case it was proved that the local group of electromagnetic gauge transformations $U(1)$ is isomorphic to both the local groups LB1 and LB2, separately, independently. LB1 on the local plane one is a group composed by the tetrad boosts $SO(1,1)$ and two different kinds of discrete transformations. One of these discrete transformations is not Lorentzian¹. LB2 on plane two is the group of spatial tetrad rotations on this plane, that is $SO(2)$. Therefore proving by transitivity that the group LB1 is isomorphic to LB2. That is, in paper¹ it was proved that the non-compact group of boosts $SO(1,1)$ plus two discrete transformations is isomorphic to the compact group $SO(2)$. Rendering the hypotheses made a priori of the no-go theorems empty. The no-go theorems from the sixties^{4,5,6} have two fundamental hypotheses made at the outset of these theorems. The internal transformations take place in an abstract space. It has been assumed that the generators of the internal and spacetime groups commute. We proved that the locally “internal” groups $SU(2)$ and $U(1)$ are isomorphic to local “spacetime” groups of tetrad transformations, and therefore the aforementioned assumption is not true simply because local Lorentz transformations do not commute in general. It has also been assumed that there are no finite dimensional unitary representations of non-compact groups. Since

LB1 groups (local boosts plus discrete transformations) are isomorphic to LB2 groups (local spatial rotations), then this is not true either, see references^{1,3}. It has been thought for a long time⁴⁻⁷ that there is no relationship between the spacetime and internal groups of local transformations. This has been proved incorrect in a manifest fashion. It was natural then to see if a similar landscape was true for superspace generalized local gauge⁸⁻¹¹ transformations of tetrads in four-dimensional spacetimes. That is, if we manage to build local tetrad skeletons that are locally invariant under the superspace generalized gauge group of transformations. We wonder if it is possible to build tetrad gauge vectors that allow to prove similar isomorphisms to the ones already proved for $U(1)$ in paper¹ or $SU(2) \times U(1)$ in manuscript³. We must make clear that we have in mind a possible geometric scenario where the extended coordinate structure is applicable. We are not talking about increasing the number of coordinates including Grassmann variables like in standard theories of strings¹², where there is an ensuing process of compactification. We are considering the possibility that these extended coordinate structures with their associated fields and Lagrangians might play a role in physics because a certain number of variables are necessary in order to build the tetrads that might undergo a local transformation from non-null into null. In this latter case, the local symmetries would be broken, however the skeleton constructions used for the purpose of proving the existence of local symmetries and invariance metric properties would be useful and suggestive for the opposite purpose of breaking symmetries. In this paper we will be working more in the sense of “internal” transformations isomorphic to LB1 and LB2 with regard to tetrad skeleton invariant constructions, following the example of paper³. However, the former possibility will be the matter of a future work. Despite of all these possible applications of these superspace extended coordinate and field structures, we must emphasize that all the results in sections II and III have mathematical validity on their own right and merit. Independent of any possible applications, the following mathematical results are true. We set out to test these results in this work, that is our purpose.

II. NEW TETRAD GENERALIZED GAUGE INVARIANT SKELETONS

Let the two-spinor θ^a transform as the fundamental representation of $SL(2, C)$ where $a = 1, 2$. The complex conjugates generate an inequivalent representation of $SL(2, C)$. The complex conjugate two-spinors will be labeled as $\bar{\theta}^{\dot{a}}$ where $\dot{a} = \dot{1}, \dot{2}$ and they transform

under the complex conjugate representation of $SL(2, C)$, see reference⁷. We know from the literature⁷⁻¹¹ and sections V-VI that we can define the following derivative operators,

$$D_a = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta^a} - \iota (\sigma^\mu \bar{\theta})_a \partial_\mu \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{D}_{\dot{a}} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{\theta}^{\dot{a}}} + \iota (\theta \sigma^\mu)_{\dot{a}} \partial_\mu . \quad (2)$$

If V is a vector superfield, we can also define⁷⁻⁹ chiral superfields $W_a = \frac{\iota}{4} \bar{D}^2 D_a V$ such that they satisfy,

$$\bar{D}_{\dot{a}} W_a = 0 . \quad (3)$$

We can also define the conjugate chiral superfields $\bar{W}_{\dot{a}}$ such that they fulfill,

$$D_a \bar{W}_{\dot{a}} = 0 . \quad (4)$$

With all these elements that can be checked in standard literature like references⁷⁻⁹ for instance, we can proceed to define two auxiliary second rank antisymmetric fields in this flat Minkowskian background.

$$\varepsilon^{\mu\nu} = W^a (\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a{}^b W_b \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}^{\mu\nu} = \bar{W}_{\dot{a}} (\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})^{\dot{a}}{}_{\dot{b}} \bar{W}^{\dot{b}} . \quad (6)$$

These two second rank antisymmetric objects in spacetime, see a discussion of the objects $(\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a{}^b$ and $(\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})^{\dot{a}}{}_{\dot{b}}$ in section V, are both local superspace generalized Abelian gauge invariants. Since we know that $(\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a{}^b = (\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})^{\dot{b}}{}_{\dot{a}}$ and $(\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})^{\dot{a}}{}_{\dot{b}} = (\sigma^{\mu\nu})_b{}^a$ we can construct the real objects,

$$\epsilon_R^{\mu\nu} = (\varepsilon^{\mu\nu} + \bar{\varepsilon}^{\mu\nu})/2 \quad (7)$$

$$\epsilon_I^{\mu\nu} = (\varepsilon^{\mu\nu} - \bar{\varepsilon}^{\mu\nu})/(2\iota) . \quad (8)$$

These two objects (7-8) possess the expected transformation properties under Lorentz transformations, see references^{13,14}. These two objects (7-8) can be used in order to build an extremal field tensor through the use of a local spacetime scalar field complexion α as,

$$\xi^{\mu\nu} = \cos \alpha \epsilon_R^{\mu\nu} - \sin \alpha \epsilon_I^{\mu\nu} , \quad (9)$$

such that the local scalar complexion α is defined by the equation $\xi_{\mu\nu} * \xi^{\mu\nu} = 0$. We define the dual second rank antisymmetric tensor as $*\xi_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\sigma\tau} \xi^{\sigma\tau}$. We can easily find, using the properties of the objects σ^α and $\bar{\sigma}^\alpha$ from references⁷⁻¹⁵ and section V that $\tan(2\alpha) = -\epsilon_{R\mu\nu} \epsilon_I^{\mu\nu} / \epsilon_{R\rho\lambda} \epsilon_R^{\rho\lambda}$. Using identities (25-26) from the first appendix, section V, it is simple to prove that $*\epsilon_R^{\mu\nu} = -\epsilon_I^{\mu\nu}$ and $*\epsilon_I^{\mu\nu} = \epsilon_R^{\mu\nu}$. This local angle α , the complexion can be studied in terms of chiral superfields through equations (5-6) and the use of identities (27-29). Like antisymmetric fields in a four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetime, the extremal fields also verify the identity,

$$\xi_{\mu\alpha} \xi^{\nu\alpha} - *\xi_{\mu\alpha} * \xi^{\nu\alpha} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_\mu^\nu Q , \quad (10)$$

where $Q = \xi_{\mu\nu} \xi^{\mu\nu}$ and Q is assumed not to be zero. Condition $\xi_{\mu\nu} * \xi^{\mu\nu} = 0$ can be proved equivalent to another condition. Through the use of the general identity,

$$A_{\mu\alpha} B^{\nu\alpha} - *B_{\mu\alpha} * A^{\nu\alpha} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_\mu^\nu A_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta} , \quad (11)$$

which is valid for every pair of antisymmetric tensors in a four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetime¹⁶, when applied to the case $A_{\mu\alpha} = \xi_{\mu\alpha}$ and $B^{\nu\alpha} = *\xi^{\nu\alpha}$ yields the equivalent condition,

$$\xi_{\rho\mu} * \xi^{\mu\nu} = 0 . \quad (12)$$

It is evident that identity (10) is a special case of (11). Next, proceeding exactly as in manuscripts^{1,2} we can introduce the following tetrad at every point in spacetime,

$$V_{(1)}^\alpha = \xi^{\alpha\lambda} \xi_{\rho\lambda} X^\rho \quad (13)$$

$$V_{(2)}^\alpha = \sqrt{-Q/2} \xi^{\alpha\lambda} X_\lambda \quad (14)$$

$$V_{(3)}^\alpha = \sqrt{-Q/2} * \xi^{\alpha\lambda} Y_\lambda \quad (15)$$

$$V_{(4)}^\alpha = *\xi^{\alpha\lambda} * \xi_{\rho\lambda} Y^\rho , \quad (16)$$

These vectors have several outstanding properties as already proven in papers^{1,2}. Two structures are present in vectors (13-16). First, the skeleton. For vector (13) the skeleton would be defined as $\xi^{\alpha\lambda} \xi_{\rho\lambda}$, for vector (15) it would be $*\xi^{\alpha\lambda}$. Second, the gauge vectors. For (13-14) the gauge vector is X^ρ , for vectors (15-16) the gauge vector is Y^ρ . Using equations (10-12) it is simple to prove that they are orthogonal. The gauge vectors have not yet been defined and will be the tool that we will use in order to prove the theorems in section III. At every point in spacetime the two vectors (13-14) define a plane or blade one^{16,17}. The two vectors (15-16) a plane or blade two, orthogonal to plane one. We remind ourselves from the results found in papers^{1,2} that the local Abelian gauge superspace invariance of the tetrad skeletons is of fundamental importance since it prevents the vectors in plane one from leaving the plane once we introduce superspace generalized local gauge transformations in the gauge vector X^ρ , and analogous for the gauge vector Y^ρ in plane two. This property ensures the invariance of the metric tensor once the vectors (13-16) are normalized. We will discuss this issue in depth in section III.

III. THEOREMS

Let us start by presenting the normalized version of tetrad (13-16),

$$U^\alpha = \xi^{\alpha\lambda} \xi_{\rho\lambda} X^\rho / (\sqrt{-Q/2} \sqrt{X_\mu \xi^{\mu\sigma} \xi_{\nu\sigma} X^\nu}) \quad (17)$$

$$V^\alpha = \xi^{\alpha\lambda} X_\lambda / (\sqrt{X_\mu \xi^{\mu\sigma} \xi_{\nu\sigma} X^\nu}) \quad (18)$$

$$Z^\alpha = *\xi^{\alpha\lambda} Y_\lambda / (\sqrt{Y_\mu * \xi^{\mu\sigma} * \xi_{\nu\sigma} Y^\nu}) \quad (19)$$

$$W^\alpha = *\xi^{\alpha\lambda} * \xi_{\rho\lambda} Y^\rho / (\sqrt{-Q/2} \sqrt{Y_\mu * \xi^{\mu\sigma} * \xi_{\nu\sigma} Y^\nu}) . \quad (20)$$

whereas Q was assumed not to be zero in the previous section II. The normalization factors are assumed not to produce divergences. Let us proceed then to make a choice for the gauge vectors. Let us consider them equal to the electromagnetic $U(1)$ potential $X^\mu = Y^\mu = A^\mu$. The field strength is given by $F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu$. We know from the theorems proved in reference¹ that the group of local electromagnetic gauge transformations is isomorphic to both the local groups of tetrad transformations LB1 and LB2, independently. We proceed then to introduce the superspace Abelian local gauge transformation of the superspace gauge potential in flat spacetime four-dimensions,

$$\delta A^\mu = \eta^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu A. \quad (21)$$

The local field A is a local scalar that defines the gauge transformation. The tensor $\eta^{\mu\nu}$ is the Minkowsky metric tensor, see section VI. We follow at this point the notation in chapter XX of reference⁷, even though the notation in other suitable references like⁸⁻⁹ is analogous. For instance, if V is a vector superfield, then the superspace generalized local gauge transformation of the vector superfield would be given by $\delta V = -\frac{i}{2} (\Lambda - \Lambda^\dagger)$, see references⁷⁻⁹. $\delta W_a = 0$, and $\delta \bar{W}_{\dot{a}} = 0$. All the ensuing proofs regarding the isomorphisms in this paper are carried out following the same steps as in papers^{1,3}. We are transforming,

$$X^\mu = Y^\mu = A^\mu \rightarrow A^\mu + \eta^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu A. \quad (22)$$

For A equal to zero we would have the identity tetrad (17-20) transformation. For A reversed in sign we would have the inverse tetrad transformation. Being additive in all their terms, these transformations (22) are associative. The Abelianity of the image of the transformations generated by these transformations is automatic. The demonstration of the injectivity and the surjectivity of these local transformations would follow the same lines as the analogous proof in paper¹. And again based on similar lines of analysis to the one carried out in manuscript¹, the image of this mapping (22) is not a subgroup of LB1. Since the steps are a mathematical replica of our isomorphism theorems already proved for the pure electromagnetic field in manuscript¹, we state these results in the following two theorems,

Theorem 1 *The mapping between the local group of supergauge Abelian transformations (22) and the local group of LB1 tetrad transformations is isomorphic.*

By similar reasoning to the one laid out in^{1,3}, in addition to all the ideas above, we can also state,

Theorem 2 *The mapping between the local group of supergauge Abelian transformations (22) and the local group of LB2 tetrad transformations is isomorphic.*

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We managed to prove new theorems regarding the “connection” between local groups of superspace Abelian generalized gauge transformations^{8–11} and local groups of tetrad transformations. These results are relevant since we are able to understand or translate abstract symmetries into spacetime symmetries that can be visualized with simplicity. We emphasize one more time that these are mathematical results completely independent of all possible conjectures that we can make regarding applications. Then we can ask about the use or application of these isomorphism theorems. Since all the local gauge symmetries can be associated to local groups of tetrad transformations^{1,2,3}, the point arises about the possibility of associating spacetimes to microparticles in four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes, like leptons for example. Because of the local group isomorphisms. All the symmetries of the Standard Model can be realized in four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetimes. We interpret the necessity of bringing about a superspace of extended coordinates and field structures, so that we have more variable room in the construction of tetrad skeletons and gauge vectors. The need for enough variables inside the skeletons and gauge vectors in order to allow for tetrad transformations from non-null into null and viceversa to take place, makes us think of an extended coordinate and field structure. When we speak of tetrads transforming locally from non-null into null, we are not talking about local groups of symmetries, otherwise the metric tensor would remain invariant. In order for a tetrad to transform from non-null into null or viceversa, we would need to destroy these local symmetries. Nonetheless, these new local supergauge invariant skeletons that we built for the opposite purpose of proving local symmetries would be useful and suggestive for the opposite goal of breaking symmetries. At the same time we believe that if all local internal symmetries of the Standard Model are isomorphic to local spacetime transformations, we can prove similar results even for these extended structures. As already stated, more in the sense of “internal” transformations isomorphic to LB1 and LB2 with regard to tetrad skeleton invariant constructions, following the example of paper³. There is a subsequent first step in extending these superspace local generalized gauge isomorphisms from a flat background into a curved background, that is, with a non-trivial gravitational field. We are also interested in constructing skeletons invariant under local supersymmetric transformations in flat and curved spacetimes. In that sense it is important as a future work, to find new tetrad skeletons that are local invariants under both,

the local superspace generalized gauge transformations, Abelian and non-Abelian, and also under the local supersymmetry transformations in spacetimes with a flat or non-flat metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. We aim at describing in Riemannian terms the many geometrical intricacies traditionally associated to quantum field theories. We quote from¹⁸ “The modern idea of the unification involves not only internal symmetries but also a new type of symmetry discovered at the beginning of the 70’s, namely, supersymmetry, which intrinsically intertwines with the former. Main features of the supersymmetry have been discussed in the talks by P. Dimopolous and S. Fayet. So, I shall remind only that supersymmetry was independently discovered by three groups of authors:

Yu. Gol’fand and E. Lichtman (1971)

D. Volkov and V. Akulov (1972)

J. Wess and B. Zumino (1974)

The motivation and starting points used by these groups were quite different. The motivation of Gol’fand and Lichtman¹⁹ was to introduce a parity violation in the quantum field theory. The starting point of the paper by Akulov and myself^{20,21} was the question whether Goldstone particles with spin one half might exist. Wess and Zumino²² performed the generalization of the supergroup which first appeared in the Neveu-Schwarz-Ramond dual model^{23,24}.

V. APPENDIX I

The object $\sigma^{\alpha\beta}$ is defined as⁷⁻¹⁴ $\sigma^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{i}{4}(\sigma^\alpha \bar{\sigma}^\beta - \sigma^\beta \bar{\sigma}^\alpha)$. The objects σ^α and $\bar{\sigma}^\alpha$ arise when building the Weyl representation for left handed and right handed spinors. According to⁷⁻¹¹, they are defined as $\sigma^\alpha = (\mathbf{1}, \sigma^i)$ and $\bar{\sigma}^\alpha = (\mathbf{1}, -\sigma^i)$, where σ^i are the Pauli matrices for $i = 1 \cdots 3$. Under the $(\frac{1}{2}, 0)$ and $(0, \frac{1}{2})$ spinor representations of the Lorentz group they transform as,

$$S_{(1/2)}^{-1} \sigma^\alpha S_{(1/2)} = \Lambda^\alpha_\gamma \sigma^\gamma \tag{23}$$

$$S_{(1/2)}^{-1} \bar{\sigma}^\alpha S_{(1/2)} = \Lambda^\alpha_\gamma \bar{\sigma}^\gamma . \tag{24}$$

Equations (23-24) mean that under the spinor representation of the Lorentz group, σ^α and $\bar{\sigma}^\alpha$ transform the same way as vectors. In (23-24), the matrices $S_{(1/2)}$ are local, as

well as Λ^α_γ , see reference¹¹. The $SU(2)$ elements can be considered to belong to the Weyl spinor representation of the Lorentz group. Since the group $SU(2)$ is homomorphic to $SO(3)$, they just represent local space rotations. It is also possible to define the object $\bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{i}{4}(\bar{\sigma}^\alpha \sigma^\beta - \bar{\sigma}^\beta \sigma^\alpha)$, analogously. Then, we have,

$$\left(\sigma^{\alpha\beta} + \bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta}\right) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \alpha = 0 \text{ and } \beta = i \\ \epsilon^{ijk} \sigma^k & \text{if } \alpha = i \text{ and } \beta = j \end{cases} ,$$

$$\left(\sigma^{\alpha\beta} - \bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta}\right) = \begin{cases} -i \sigma^i & \text{if } \alpha = 0 \text{ and } \beta = i \\ 0 & \text{if } \alpha = i \text{ and } \beta = j \end{cases} .$$

We can state for example self and antiself duality properties of these objects⁹ $\sigma^{\alpha\beta}$ and $\bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta}$,

$$\sigma^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2i} \epsilon^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \sigma_{\gamma\delta} \quad (25)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}^{\alpha\beta} = -\frac{1}{2i} \epsilon^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \bar{\sigma}_{\gamma\delta} . \quad (26)$$

From reference¹⁴ we also know that,

$$(\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a^b (\sigma_{\mu\nu})_c^d = 2\delta_a^d \delta_c^b - \delta_a^b \delta_c^d \quad (27)$$

$$(\bar{\sigma}^{\mu\nu})_{\dot{a}}^{\dot{b}} (\bar{\sigma}_{\mu\nu})_{\dot{c}}^{\dot{d}} = 2\delta_{\dot{a}}^{\dot{d}} \delta_{\dot{c}}^{\dot{b}} - \delta_{\dot{a}}^{\dot{b}} \delta_{\dot{c}}^{\dot{d}} \quad (28)$$

$$(\sigma^{\mu\nu})_a^b (\bar{\sigma}_{\mu\nu})_{\dot{c}}^{\dot{d}} = 0 . \quad (29)$$

For $SL(2, C)$ group elements M , the analogous equations to (23-24) are¹⁴,

$$M^{-1} \sigma^\alpha (M^{-1})^\dagger = \Lambda^\alpha_\gamma \sigma^\gamma \quad (30)$$

$$M^\dagger \bar{\sigma}^\alpha M = \Lambda^\alpha_\gamma \bar{\sigma}^\gamma . \quad (31)$$

We follow in general the notation in⁹ and since we will not write all these objects properties, we cite fundamentally the references⁷⁻¹⁴.

VI. APPENDIX II

We are introducing in this second appendix more objects that we will need in order to construct the tetrads⁷⁻¹⁵. Either the “skeleton” of the tetrad, or the “gauge vector” fields X^μ and Y^μ . We start with the Hermitian matrices σ_{ab}^μ introduced by Infeld and van der Waerden,

$$\sigma_{ab}^\mu \sigma^{\nu ab} = \eta^{\mu\nu} . \quad (32)$$

In this work on a flat background, $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is the Minkowsky metric tensor in four-dimensional spacetime with signature $(-+++)$. Latin indices are the spinor indices taking values 0 and 1, while the primed latin indices refer to the complex conjugate taking values $\dot{0}$ and $\dot{1}$. A detailed discussion is included in reference¹⁵ chapter eight. Therefore we summarize the main relations and expressions involved in our work.

$$\sigma_{ab}^\mu \sigma_{cd}^\nu \eta_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{abcd} . \quad (33)$$

$$\eta_{abcd} = \epsilon_{ac} \epsilon_{bd} . \quad (34)$$

ϵ_{ac} and $\epsilon_{\dot{b}\dot{d}}$ are the skew symmetric Levi-Civita metric spinors, both with components $\epsilon_{00} = \epsilon_{\dot{0}\dot{0}} = 0$, $\epsilon_{01} = \epsilon_{\dot{0}\dot{1}} = -1$, $\epsilon_{11} = \epsilon_{\dot{1}\dot{1}} = 0$ and $\epsilon_{10} = \epsilon_{\dot{1}\dot{0}} = 1$.

$$\theta_a = \epsilon_{ab} \theta^b \quad (35)$$

$$\theta^a = \epsilon^{ab} \theta_b . \quad (36)$$

The metric spinors ϵ^{ab} and $\epsilon^{\dot{b}\dot{d}}$ with components $\epsilon^{00} = \epsilon^{\dot{0}\dot{0}} = 0$, $\epsilon^{01} = \epsilon^{\dot{0}\dot{1}} = 1$, $\epsilon^{11} = \epsilon^{\dot{1}\dot{1}} = 0$ and $\epsilon^{10} = \epsilon^{\dot{1}\dot{0}} = -1$. θ^a are local two-spinors, the index $a = 1, 2$ spanning a complex two dimensional vector space \mathcal{C} at each spacetime point, see reference¹⁵, chapter ten. In the complex conjugate to this vector space $\bar{\mathcal{C}}$ the indices are raised and lowered using the $\epsilon_{\dot{b}\dot{d}}$ metric spinor,

$$\bar{\theta}_{\dot{a}} = \epsilon_{\dot{a}\dot{b}} \bar{\theta}^{\dot{b}} \quad (37)$$

$$\bar{\theta}^{\dot{a}} = \epsilon^{\dot{a}\dot{b}} \bar{\theta}_{\dot{b}} . \quad (38)$$

Since ϵ^{ab} belongs to the tensor product $\mathcal{C} \otimes \mathcal{C}$, it transforms under $SL(2, C)$ as,

$$\epsilon'^{ab} = \epsilon^{cd} S_c^a S_d^b = (\det S) \epsilon^{ab} , \quad (39)$$

where $\det S$ stands for the determinant of the $SL(2, C)$ transformation S_a^b , which means that $\det S = 1$. ϵ^{ab} is a metric spinor, that is why it is used for raising and lowering spinor indices. Likewise for $\epsilon^{\dot{a}\dot{b}}$.

REFERENCES

- ¹A. Garat, J. Math. Phys. **46**, 102502 (2005). A. Garat, Erratum: Tetrads in geometrodynamics, J. Math. Phys. **55**, 019902 (2014).
- ²A. Garat, Euler observers in geometrodynamics, Int. J. Geom. Meth. Mod. Phys., Vol. **11** (2014), 1450060. arXiv:gr-qc/1306.4005
- ³A. Garat, Gravitation and Cosmology, 2014 Vol. **20** No. 1, pp. 116-126. Pleiades Publishing Ltd. arXiv:gr-qc/0602049.
- ⁴S. Weinberg, Phys. Rev. **139**, B597 (1965).
- ⁵L. ORaifeartagh, Phys. Rev. **139**, B1052 (1965).
- ⁶S. Coleman and J. Mandula, Phys. Rev. **159**, N5 1251 (1967).
- ⁷M. Kaku, *Quantum Field Theory: A Modern Introduction* (Oxford University Press, New York, 1993).
- ⁸I. Aitchison, *Supersymmetry in Particle Physics* (Cambridge University Press, 2007).
- ⁹F. Quevedo, *Supersymmetry, University of Cambridge* (www.damtp.cam.ac.uk/user/fq201/susynotes.pdf, 2006).
- ¹⁰M. Srednicki, *Quantum Field Theory* (Cambridge University Press, New York, 2007).
- ¹¹S. Weinberg, *The Quantum Theory of Fields, Volume III, Supersymmetry* (Cambridge University Press, New York, 2005).

- ¹²J. Polchinski, *String Theory, Volume II, Superstring Theory and Beyond* (Cambridge University Press, New York, 2005).
- ¹³S. P. Martin, *A supersymmetry primer*, (2011) (arXiv:hep-th/9709356v6 [hep-ph]).
- ¹⁴H. K. Dreiner, H. E. Haber and S. P. Martin, *Two-component spinor techniques and Feynman rules for quantum field theory and supersymmetry*, Phys. Rept. **494**:1-196, (2010) (arXiv:hep-th/0812.1594 [hep-ph]).
- ¹⁵M. Carmeli, *Classical Fields: General Relativity and Gauge Theory* (J. Wiley & Sons, New York, 1982).
- ¹⁶C. Misner and J. A. Wheeler, Annals of Physics **2**, 525 (1957).
- ¹⁷J. A. Schouten, *Ricci Calculus: An Introduction to Tensor Calculus and Its Geometrical Applications* (Springer, Berlin, 1954).
- ¹⁸D. Volkov, *Supergravity before 1976* (Talk given at: International conference on history of original ideas and basic discoveries in particle physics, Erice, Italy, 29 jul-4 aug 1994).
- ¹⁹Yu. Gol'fand and E. Lichtman, JETP Letters **13** (1971) 323.
- ²⁰D. Volkov and V. Akulov, JETP Letters **16** (1972) 438. Phys. Lett. **46B** (1973) 109.
- ²¹D. Volkov and V. Akulov, Theor. Math. Phys. **18** (1974) 28.
- ²²J. Wess and B. Zumino, Nucl. Phys. **B70** (1974) 39.
- ²³J. L. Gervais and B. Sakita, Nucl. Phys. **B34** (1971) 633.
- ²⁴A. Neveu and J. Schwarz, Nucl. Phys. **B31** (1971) 86. P. Ramond, Phys. Rev. **D3** (1971) 2415.